

PEDAGOGIKA, PSIXOLOGIYA VA IJTIMOIY TADQIQOTLAR

Onlayn ilmiy jurnal

Jild: 03 Nashr: 09 (2024)

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASAL VERBS IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

Makhsutaliyeva Feruzabonu Kakhramon kizi
Student of Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash muammolari, bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashning jismoniy, shaxsiy (ruhiy), aqliy, maxsus tayyorgarlik bosqichlari haqida so'z yuritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Phrasal verbs, English language.*

Introduction

Phrasal verbs, which typically consist of a verb combined with one or more particles (prepositions or adverbs), are a distinctive feature of English. They can pose challenges for learners due to their idiomatic nature. However, many languages have similar constructions that serve comparable functions. Here's a comparative analysis of phrasal verbs in English and some other languages:

1. English

- Characteristics: English has a vast array of phrasal verbs (e.g., "give up," "look after," "run into"). They often have meanings that are not immediately obvious from the individual words.

- Usage: Phrasal verbs are commonly used in both spoken and informal written English, making them crucial for fluency.

- Challenges: Non-native speakers may struggle with the idiomatic meanings and the flexibility of word order (e.g., "I looked it up" vs. "I looked up it").

2. German

- Characteristics: German uses separable verbs (e.g., "aufstehen" - to stand up) which can be split into two parts based on sentence structure (e.g., "Ich stehe um 7 Uhr auf" - I get up at 7 o'clock).

- Usage: Like English phrasal verbs, these constructions are common, but they tend to be more regular and predictable in meaning.

- Challenges: The separation of prefixes can confuse learners regarding verb placement in sentences.

3. Spanish

- Characteristics: Spanish often uses compound verbs or verb phrases with prepositions (e.g., "dar cuenta de" - to account for). While not directly equivalent to English phrasal verbs, they serve similar purposes.

- Usage: These constructions are prevalent in conversational Spanish and convey nuances similar to those found in English phrasal verbs.

- Challenges: The challenge for learners lies in mastering the appropriate preposition that accompanies certain verbs.

4. French

- Characteristics: French employs verbal phrases using prepositions (e.g., "faire attention à" - to pay attention to). While there aren't direct equivalents to phrasal verbs, certain usages resemble them.

- Usage: These phrases are essential for fluency and often carry unique meanings that differ from their individual components.

- Challenges: Understanding which prepositions pair correctly with verbs can be difficult for learners.

5. Chinese

- Characteristics: Mandarin utilizes resultative verb complements and directional complements rather than phrasal verbs per se (e.g., “去” qù meaning “to go” combined with a verb).

- Usage: The structure conveys complex actions but does not emulate the flexibility of English phrasal verbs directly.

- Challenges: Learners must grasp how different complements modify the meaning of base verbs.

Comparative Observations:

1. Idiomatic Nature:

- Both English and Spanish have idiomatic expressions tied closely to their respective cultures, while German's separable prefixes offer clearer semantic clues.

2. Flexibility vs Structure:

- English allows significant flexibility with word order when using phrasal verbs, whereas German has strict rules on prefix placement.

3. Cultural Nuances:

- Each language carries cultural nuances reflected through its usage of these constructs; understanding these is vital for effective communication.

4. Learning Challenges:

- Regardless of language, learners face difficulties related to idiomatic meanings, appropriate usage contexts, and grammatical structures surrounding these forms. Phrasal verbs are combinations of verbs with prepositions or adverbs that create a meaning different from the original verb. They are particularly prevalent in English, but many languages have similar constructs, though they may not be directly called "phrasal verbs. Examples:

1. Give up - to stop trying.

- I decided to give up smoking.

2. Look after - to take care of.

- Can you look after my cat while I'm away?

3. Run into - to meet unexpectedly.

- I ran into an old friend at the store.

Analysis:

Phrasal verbs in English can often be idiomatic, meaning their combined meaning is not easily inferred from the individual words. They can also vary in separability:

- Separable: Turn off the lights or Turn the lights off.

- Inseparable: Run into someone (cannot separate "run" and "into").

In Spanish, equivalent constructs are often referred to as "locuciones verbales" or "verbos compuestos."

Examples:

1. Dejar de (to stop doing something)

- Voy a dejar de fumar. (I'm going to stop smoking.)

2. Dar con (to find/come across)

- No puedo dar con la solución. (I can't come across the solution.)

3. Contar con (to count on)

- Puedes contar conmigo. (You can count on me.)

Analysis:

Spanish phrasal forms often involve prepositions that modify the verb's meaning significantly, similar to English. However, they do not always follow the same patterns of separability. German utilizes similar constructs known as "trennbare Verben" (separable verbs).

Examples:

1. Aufstehen (to get up)

- Ich stehe um sieben Uhr auf. (I get up at seven o'clock.)

2. Anrufen (to call someone)

- Ich rufe dich morgen an. (I'll call you tomorrow.)

3. Mitkommen (to come along)

- Kommst du mit? (Are you coming along?)

Analysis:

In German, separable prefixes can change the meaning of a verb entirely and are usually placed before the main verb in a sentence when conjugated. French does not have phrasal verbs in exactly the same way but uses verbal phrases or constructions that serve a similar purpose.

Examples:

1. Se moquer de (to mock/tease)

- Ne te moque pas de moi! (Don't mock me!)

2. S'occuper de (to take care of)

- Je m'occupe des enfants. (I take care of the children.)

3. Rendre visite à (to visit someone)

- Nous allons rendre visite à nos amis. (We are going to visit our friends.)

Analysis:

French constructions often require reflexive pronouns or additional prepositions that modify standard verbs and convey specific meanings. Phrasal verbs exist in many languages under different names and structures but serve a common function of providing nuanced meanings through

combinations of words. Understanding these can greatly enhance language learning as they reflect cultural idioms and expressions unique to each language context.

In conclusion, while different languages exhibit various systems akin to phrasal verbs, each has unique characteristics that reflect its grammar rules and cultural context. Understanding these differences is crucial for language acquisition and effective communication across linguistic boundaries.

REFERENCES

1. Hart, C. W. (2020). *Phrasal Verbs*. [Publisher information if available].
2. Murphy, R. (1999). *The Ultimate Phrasal Verb Book*. [Publisher information if available].
3. McCarthy, M., & O'Dell, F. (2004). *English Phrasal Verbs in Use*. Cambridge University Press.
4. Biber, D., Conrad, S., & Reppen, R. (1998). *Corpus Linguistics: Investigating Language Structure and Use*. Cambridge University Press.
5. Lewis, M. (1993). *The Lexical Approach: The State of ELT and a Way Forward*. Language Teaching Publications.
6. Nation, I. S. P. (2001). *Learning Vocabulary in Another Language*. Cambridge University Press.
7. Schmitt, N., & Carter, R. (2004). *Formulaic Sequences in Action: An Introduction to the Study of Phraseology*. In N. Schmitt (Ed.), *Formulaic Sequences* (pp. 1-22). John Benjamins Publishing Company.
8. Boers, F., & Lindstromberg, S. (2008). *Cognitive Linguistic Approaches to Teaching Vocabulary and Phraseology*. In F. Boers & S. Lindstromberg (Eds.), *Expanding the Lexicon* (pp. 1-16). Peter Lang.
9. Celce-Murcia, M., & Larsen-Freeman, D. (1999). *The Grammar Book: An ESL/EFL Teacher's Course*. Heinle & Heinle.
10. Thornbury, S. (2002). *How to Teach Vocabulary*. Pearson Education.